

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14621940

Dynamic Capabilities Of Organisations And Corporate Agility Of Food And Beverages Firms In Rivers State, Nigeria

Eboigbe Ernest Ifeanyi

Department of Management
Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Port Harcourt, of Port Harcourt, Nigeria
ernesteboigbe@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated dynamic capabilities of organisations and corporate agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Three objectives, research questions and hypotheses guided the study. Correlation research design was employed for the study with population of 161 managers and supervisors of 6 food and beverage organisations in Rivers State. Sample size was not adopted for the study considering the total population. Thus, the total population served as the sample size. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire of two set titled: Dynamic Capabilities of Organisations Scale (DCOS) and Corporate Agility Scale (CAS), which was used to source for data. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.83 for DCOS and CAS respectively were obtained using Cronbach alpha statistics. Spearman Correlation was used to answer the research questions, as well as to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a strong relationship between sensing capability, learning capability, integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Hence, it was concluded that dynamic capabilities of organisations are instrumental in ensuring corporate agility of the food and beverage firms in Rivers State. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended among others that, the employees of the food and beverage firms should ensure that they maintain high level of sensing capability in all their dealings as such will help to enhance their agility. Also, the management of the food and beverage firms should maintain high learning capability in their day-to-day activities as such will help to enhance the agility of the firm.

Keywords: Dynamic, Capabilities, Organisations, Corporate Agility

INTRODUCTION

Generally, organisations are operating in a very dynamic atmosphere which is characterized with high level of uncertainty. Business organisations are faced with challenges as a result of the volatility and instability in the dynamic business world. Business organizations are frequently faced with an unprecedented and growing number of possible disruptions to their current state; thus, notable businesses usually fail if proper risk management models to adopt agility metrics are not employed (Akgun, cited in Barinua & Nwimua, 2022). In line with the above assertion, Annarelli et al (2020) opined that the present-day firms operate in environment characterized with unprecedented changes arising from competitive forces as well as other factors within the business sphere. The study added that firms' survival and

sustainability require being equipped with indispensable capabilities that will allow for strategic response to market forces. In this present business domain, which is characterized with high proliferation in technology and high business failures, only organizations that possess high agility capability are most likely to withstand the turbulent moment and imponderable varieties in the business world (Barinua & Nwimua, 2022).

Furthermore, firms apply laid down principles that guide their mechanisms for survival and fight against disruptions that may appear to cut short their corporate existence. Similarly, Stronen et al. (2017) noted that a firm's survival depends more on the activities carried out before such a disruption occurs than on the actions it takes as the disruption surfaces making corporate agility a critical aspect of business management. Corporate agility is the ability a firm has to continue its function and excel despite the difficulties it faces within the complex business atmosphere. A high degree of corporate or firms' agility strengthens business stability, competitiveness, profitability and shareholders' value (Hearnshaw & Wilson 2013). In other words, agility as an organisational attribute, enables businesses to withstand turbulent elements within the business environment and boost ability to survive the test of time. In alignment with the above assertion, the absence of corporate agility makes it very difficult for business organisations to operate effectively when confronted with worries in the industry especially with the presence of highly competitive forces.

Considering the volatile nature of the business domain, it is important that organisations possess some dynamic capabilities in order to operate more effectively and attain their desired goals. The dynamic capabilities of organisation deal with the way that organisations identify opportunities, develop new knowledge, internal dissemination of information and launch new services or products in the market (Teece, 2011). Amin, Budiastuti, So and Arief (2019) contended that dynamic capability of organisation help boost the performance of organisation by enabling the firm to identify and effectively respond to the opportunities by developing new processes, services and products. The capability of organisations, then from rivalries in the industry (Stronen et al., 2017). It is argued that dynamic capabilities are a higher-order capability to build/create, integrate and effectively reconfigure operational capabilities. Teece, Pisano and Shuen as cited Barinua and Nwimua (2022) did an extensive work on the dynamic capabilities of organisation where they defined dynamic capability as the strategic and organisational routines, utilised by managers in order to alter firms resource base and renew capabilities so as to create or build new sources of competitive edge.

Wang et al (2019) defined dynamic capabilities of organisation as a firm's ability to effectively integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to respond to the rapidly changing business atmosphere. It is important that organisations enhance their dynamic capabilities in order to cope with environmental challenges (Wulandari, et al., 2021). Over the years, several scholars have examined ways to enhance the resilience of organizations using various constructs. Despite several scholarly work, there are scanty work on how dynamic capability of organisations relates with corporate agility. It was on this premise that this study examined dynamic capabilities of organisations and corporate agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Business organisationa all over the world especially in fast developing countries like Nigeria have been highly affect by the various environmental dynamics and this issue has degenerated overtime due to some factors like removal of fuel subsidy and the outbreak of the Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19). The issue of poor organisational resilience has affected their resilience capacity such as agility. The unexpected economic downturn has changed current organisational narratives which has also hampered business existence and made corporate agility critical. This has manifested in low adaptive size, poor profitability, poor competitive advantage, low agility and ultimately the liquidation of the firm. Poor organisational agility leads to inability to stay abreast and adapt to unfavourable realities. Low organisational agility could also affect the performance and competitiveness of the firms.

The high rate at which firms fade away after few years of inception has made the issue of agility more critical thereby making business survival more colossal for managers to handle. Similarly, Barinua and

Nwimua (2022) observed that the idea behind striving for corporate agility is to enable organisations make away with negative effective of sudden economic crises, adapt appropriate to the current changes and survive the dynamic business forces. The problem of low agility of firms still persists despite all attempts in previous years to address the issue. Hence, this study examined how dynamic capabilities of organisations relate with corporate agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between dynamic capabilities of organisations and corporate agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. determine the relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. ascertain the relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
3. find out the relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions served as a tentative answer to the research questions.

1. What is the relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the following null hypothesis;

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarifications

Dynamic Capabilities of Organisations

Organisation's capacity to incorporate, develop, and reconfigure internal and external competences in order to respond to rapidly evolving conditions. Ability (or capacity) as well as processes or routines have been described as dynamic capabilities (Teece et al., 1997). Organisational capabilities are deep-rooted in the routines, frameworks, and processes of the enterprise. These routines can be seen in the organisation's operations, processes, cultures, and senior leadership's attitude, to name a few. Further explanation, "capabilities" highlights the critical role of strategic management in adapting, integrating, and reconfiguring internal and external organisational expertise, tools, and functional competences to meet the evolving environments requirements. Dynamic capabilities, according to Zahra and George (2002), are basically change-oriented capabilities that assist companies in redeploying and reconfiguring their capital base to satisfy changing customer needs and competitors' strategies. Dynamic capabilities, according to Zollo and Winter (2002), are mastered and consistent patterns of group operation from which an enterprise routinely generates and modifies its working routines in the direction of greater effectiveness. Dynamic capabilities, according to Winter (2003), are those that work to expand, alter, or establish ordinary capabilities.

Dynamic capabilities, according to Teece (2017), include sensing, seizing, and transforming capabilities. However, Barinua and Nwimua (2022) saw these capabilities as dimensions of organizational dynamic capabilities, and they include: sensing, learning and integrating capabilities.

- i. **Sensing capability:** Sensing capability is the ability of organisation to detect, perceive and seek opportunities in the business environment (Pavlou & El Sawy, 2011). Scan, search, and exploration are required to detect opportunities and threats, especially in rapidly changing markets. In operational terminology, this entails a set of tools and routines such as a strategy-making mechanism that incorporates variation, resources dedicated to competitive analysis and technical progress monitoring, and platforms for discussion of potential prospects. Subtly, and in addition to the requisite resources, this capability requires a balance of centralization and decentralization of control to encourage feedback from market-facing units, an open culture that fosters debate, senior leaders' commitment of resources (financial and time) to encourage long-term thinking, and a senior management team that fosters a long-term mindset and practice (Burgelman, 2002).
- ii. **Learning capability:** This is defined as a firm's characteristics and managerial attributes geared toward the promotion and support of a learning process. It consists of the resources that the company needs to diagnose the need for employee training, evaluate ineffective business practices, and carry out the process of sharing information and knowledge gained among the staff (Fang, et al., 2011). According to Santos-Vijande et al. (2012), learning capacity is a crucial resource that improves a company's productivity, inventiveness, and performance. The ability to learn helps company increase productivity, identify market opportunities, change business operations, reduce costs, and introduce new product delivery strategies to the market (Sok & O'Cass, 2011). It determines a small business's ability to compete, develop, and grow (Jerez-Gómez, et al., 2005). A significant competitive advantage is created by SMEs firms that successfully establish and constantly improve their learning capabilities (Clements, 2010).
- iii. **Integration capability:** Integration capability has to do with the business structure competency that works to fully understand the organisational structure, connected assets, associations, and ideas between the connected assets and the business, as well as how the structure and benefits are operated (Gewertz, 2016). It is defined as the participation of existing proficiencies into the company organisation, associating and integrating them with current assets and competencies (Teece, 2007). In order to combine modern intellect with the contemporary brainpower cornerstone, integration calls for the bringing together of varied assets. This depends on internally advanced, mutually coherent intelligences, the acquisition of external assets, and the synthesis of available resources. A highly important component is dynamic capabilities since it helps maintain the change that intelligence formulation establishes (Verona and Ravasi, 2003).

Corporate Agility

Agility is one of the measures of corporate resilience. It is defined as an effective integration of response capabilities and knowledge management so that the unforeseen (or unpredictable) changes in both proactive and responsive business and customer needs and opportunities can be adapted quickly, efficiently, and accurately without compromising on the cost or quality of the product and process (Ganguly, et al., 2009). Corporate agility refers to the range of ways in which success is achieved. High flexibility means an active capacity and a readiness to recognize new options, overcome inertia and cater for unstructured situations, rather than being reduced to a few defined solutions (e.g., unanticipated change) (Barinua & Nwimua, 2022). Corporate agility is defined as the ability to change an organization quickly, efficiently and sustainably; a replicable organizational resource" (Worley, et al., 2014).

Corporate agility is also referred as the capacity of an organization, as internal and external circumstances warrant, to efficiently redeploy and redirect its resources to value creation and value protection. Apart from managing demand shocks of Stigler, agile organizations need to manage uncertainty on the supply side and adjust strategy if necessary and desired. As an autonomous concept, organizational agility is limited by its management guidance. There is an implicit role of managers. The economic system has to choose how to respond to demand fluctuations and other surprises by putting routines and self-organization on one side (Barinua & Nwimua, 2022). Agility can be described as the organizational

ability to identify opportunities faster than competitors and take advantage of them. Due to the increased significance of meaning and response to environmental changes, it is highlighted as a key capability.

In a knowledge-rich environment to provide customer-driven products and services in a rapidly changing market environment, Yusuf, et al (1999) define agility as the successful exploration of competitive bases (speed, flexibility, proactivity for innovation, quality and profitability) through the integration of reconfigurable resources and best practices. Sambamurthy, et al. (2003) define agility as the capacity of a company to identify opportunities and threats, assemble the assets and skills needed to launch an adequate response, judge its advantages and risks, and implement competitively rapid action. Agility is one of the keys to solving the problem when there is turbulence in an environment. Agility is utilized for reacting in the turbulent business environment to unexpected changes. Agility is strong and fast; it needs creativity and innovation (Gilaninia & Resvani, 2011).

Corporate agility is the capacity of the organization to survive and to thrive in a changing, unpredictable environment (Karami, 2007). Agility is an integrated result of alertness to changes – both internally and environmentally – that allows resources to respond (proactively/reactively) to these changes, all at an expeditious, flexible, affordable, relieved of their responsiveness. No one alertness or responsiveness gives agility individually. To achieve agility, both competencies are needed. Warning as well as responsiveness must be timely, flexible, affordable and appropriate. The effective integration of these two competences can lead to greater competitiveness. The result is a relatively comprehensive and unified conception of agility by including fundamental points that meet previous definitions (Holsapple & Li 2008). If all resources are fully committed, agility will be reduced – degrees of freedom to be aware of or responsive will be reduced and the organization will become less agile.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional survey research was employed for this study because it allows us to get an instantaneous look at the outcomes and characteristics of the food and beverage companies. The population of the study consisted of 161 managers and supervisors from 6 Rivers state food and beverage businesses that are members of the Food and Beverage Association of Nigeria (MAN). These organisations were chosen since they could provide the information needed for the study. In view of the population covered, no sample size was drawn or computed. Through Google structures, where respondents were given a URL to see poll and present their responses, data were gathered. A questionnaire of two sets was the instrument for the study, and it was titled: Dynamic Capabilities of Organisations Scale (DCOS) and Corporate Agility Scale (CAS). It was responded to on a 4-point Likert-like scale, where 1 is the most grounded objection and 4 is the most grounded understanding. Somewhere in the range of 3 and 4, 3 demonstrates arrangement and 4 shows solid understanding. Cronbach alpha reliability method was utilized to calculate the reliability coefficients of the instrument which yielded 0.87 and 0.83 for Dynamic Capabilities of Organisations Scale and Corporate Agility Scale respectively. For data analysis, Spearman Correlation was adopted to answer the research questions and also the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. 161 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, but a total of 141 copies were retrieved, resulting in 88% retrieval rate.

RESULTS

The results of the analysed data for each research questions and its corresponding hypothesis are presented on tables.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Sensing Capability and Agility

Correlations			Sensing Capability	Agility
Spearman's rho	Sensing Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.644**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Agility	Correlation Coefficient	.644**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

Scale of Measurement: 0.76 - 1.00 = Very Strong, 0.51 - 0.75 = Strong, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak or Low, 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Low

To answer the research question 1, data on Table 1 produced a correlation coefficient, $\rho = 0.644$ between sensing capability and agility; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. For hypothesis 1 tested, it was revealed from Table 1 that the correlation for hypothesis one shows a significant relationship between sensing capability and adaptability at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), $\rho = 0.644$. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_{01}), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (H_{a1}) thus, there is a significant relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (H₀₂): There is no significant relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Learning Capability and Agility

Correlations			Learning Capability	Agility
Spearman's rho	Learning Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.625**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Agility	Correlation Coefficient	.625**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

Scale of Measurement: 0.76 - 1.00 = Very Strong, 0.51 - 0.75 = Strong, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak or Low, 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Low

To answer the research question 2, data on Table 2 produced a correlation coefficient, $\rho = 0.625$ between learning capability and agility; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. For hypothesis 2 tested, it was revealed from Table 2 that the correlation for hypothesis two shows a significant relationship between learning capability and agility at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), $\rho = 0.625$. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (H_{a2}) thus, there is a

significant relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Hypothesis (Ho₃): There is no significant relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Integrating Capability and Agility

			Correlations	
			Integrating Capability	Agility
Spearman's rho	Integrating Capability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.567**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	141	141
	Agility	Correlation Coefficient	.567**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	141	141

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Output on Research Data, 2024

Scale of Measurement: 0.76 - 1.00 = Very Strong, 0.51 - 0.75 = Strong, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak or Low, 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Low

To answer the research question 3, data on Table 3 produced a correlation coefficient, rho = 0.567 between integrating capability and agility; this value is high and positive, indicating that there is a strong relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

For hypothesis 3 tested, it was revealed from Table 3 that the correlation for hypothesis three shows a significant relationship between learning capability and agility at $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), rho = 0.567. We therefore reject the null hypothesis (Ho₃), and upheld the alternate hypothesis (Ha₃) thus, there is a significant relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first result of the study showed that there is a strong relationship between sensing capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The bivariate hypotheses between sensing capability and agility reveal a noteworthy relationship between the two variables. The Spearman correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) which implies that sensing capability has a significant relationship with agility. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.644. reveals that there is a positive significant relationship between sensing capability and agility. Thus, sensing capability will help enhance agility. A coefficient of determination of 0.415 implies that 41.5% total variation in the agility is accounted for by sensing capability. Thus, the second objective of the study which sought to examine if sensing capability relates with agility was achieved. This finding agrees with that of Osisioma et al. (2016) whose findings revealed a significant positive relationship between sensing capability and performance of First Bank Nigeria Plc and United Bank for Africa Plc in Awka. It also aligns with Chukwuemeka and Onuoha, (2018) that revealed that dynamic capabilities are related to competitive advantage of fast foods restaurants.

The second finding of the study revealed that there is a strong relationship between learning capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The bivariate hypotheses between learning capability and agility reveal a significant relationship between the two variables. The Spearman

Rank correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) which implies that learning capability has a significant relationship with agility. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.625 reveals that there is a strong positive significant relationship between sensing capability and agility. Thus, enhancing sensing capability will help enhance agility. A coefficient of determination of 0.391 implies that 39.1% total variation in the agility of an organization is accounted for by learning capability. Thus, the fourth objective of the study which sought to examine if learning capability relates with agility was achieved. This finding conforms with that of Banerjee, Farooq and Upadhyaya, (2018) whose findings reveals significant relationship between dynamic capabilities, competitive advantage and organisational performance. It aligns with Singh, Charan and Chattopadhyay, (2019) whose findings reveals that dynamic capabilities is related to responsiveness.

The third finding of the showed that there is a strong relationship between integrating capability and agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The bivariate hypotheses between integrating capability and agility reveal a noteworthy relationship between the two variables. The Spearman Rank correlation coefficient reveals that the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$) which implies that integrating capability has a moderate significant relationship with agility. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. The result of the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.513 reveals that there is a strong positive significant relationship between integrating capability and agility. Thus, enhancing integrating capability will help enhance agility. A coefficient of determination of 0.263 implies that 26.3% total variation in the agility of an organization is accounted for by integrating capability. Thus, the first objective of the study which sought to examine if integrating capability relates with agility was achieved. This finding agrees with that of Christopher and Peck, 2004; Jüttner and Maklan, (2011), whose findings shows that integration between 3PLs and customers can enhance the timing and accuracy of shared information, and provide logistical services to customers. It aligns with Braunscheidel et al., 2010, 2014, Zhao et al., 2013 that external integration has a favourable impact on service performance, including customer satisfaction and delivery quality.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the concludes that, there is strong and significant relationship between dynamic capabilities of organisation and corporate agility of food and beverages firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Hence, dynamic capabilities of organisation in terms of sensing capability, learning capability and integrating capability are instrumental in ensuring corporate agility of the food and beverage firms in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The employees of the food and beverage firms should ensure that they maintain high level of sensing capability in all their dealings as such will help to enhance their agility.
2. The management of the food and beverage firms should maintain high learning capability in their day-to-day activities as such will help enhance the agility of the firm.
3. Organisations should continue to adopt high integrating capability to encourage the corporate agility.

REFERENCES

- Achebelama, T.C. & Achebelema, S.D. (2021). Collaborative management and organisational resilience: Evidence from the oil and gas industry of a developing economy. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 1(5), 1-15.
- Annarelli, A., Battistella, C., & Nonino, F. (2020). A framework to evaluate the effects of organisational resilience on service quality. *Sustainability*, 12, 958–963.

- Banerjee, C. S., Farooq, A., & Upadhyaya, S. (2018). The relationship between dynamic capabilities, competitive advantage & organisational performance. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, 6(3), 603-610.
- Braunscheidel, M.J., Suresh, N.C. & Boisnier, A.D. (2010). Investigating the impact of organisational culture on supply chain integration, *Human Resource Management*, 49(5), 883-911.
- Burgelman, R.A. (2002). *Strategy is destiny: How strategy-making shapes a company's future*. Free Press.
- Christopher, M. & Peck, H. (2004). Building the resilient supply chain”, *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 15 (2), 1-14.
- Chukwuemeka, O. W., & Onuoha, B. C. (2018). Dynamic capabilities and competitive advantage of fast foods restaurants. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 4(3), 7-14.
- Clements, M. D. (2010). Building learning capability: Enhancing the learning talent chain by connecting environments. Development and learning in organisations. *An International Journal*, 24(1), 7-9.
- Ganguly, A., Nilchiani, R. & Farr, J. V. (2009). Evaluating agility in corporate enterprises. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 118(2), 410-423.
- Gewertz, C. (2016). Are dual-enrolment programs being oversold? *Education Week*, 36(2), 12-13.
- Hearnshaw, E. J. S. & Wilson, M. M. J. (2013). A complex network approach to supply chain network theory. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 33(4), 76-87.
- Hearnshaw, E. J. S. & Wilson, M. M. J. (2013). A complex network approach to supply chain network theory. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 33(4), 76-87.
- Holsapple, C.W. & Li, X. (2008). Understanding Organizational Agility: A Work-Design Perspective. *13th International Command and Control Research and Technology Symposia (ICCRTS 2008)*, 17-19.
- Jerez-Gómez, P., Céspedes-Lorente, J., & Valle-Cabrera, R. (2005). Organisational learning capability: A proposal of measurement. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(6), 715-725.
- Jüttner, U. & Maklan, S. (2011), “Supply chain resilience in the global financial crisis: an empirical study. Supply Chain Management. *An International Journal*, 16(4), 246-259.
- Osisoma, H., Nzewi, H., & Mgbemena, I. (2016). Dynamic capabilities and performance of selected commercial banks in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and social sciences*, 4(10).
- Pavlou, P. A. & El Sawy, O. A. (2011). Understanding the elusive black box of dynamic capabilities. *Decision Sciences*, 42(1), 65-77.
- Sambamurthy, V., Bharadwaj, A., & Grover, V. (2003). Shaping agility through digital options: Reconceptualizing the role of information technology in contemporary firms. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(2), 237-263.
- Santos-Vijande, M. L., López-Sánchez, J. Á., & Trespalacios, J. A. (2012). How organisational learning affects a firm's flexibility, competitive strategy, and performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(8), 1079-1089. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.09.002>
- Singh, R., Charan, P., & Chattopadhyay, M. (2019). Dynamic capabilities and responsiveness: moderating effect of organisation structures and environmental dynamism. *Decision*, 46(4), 301-319.
- Sok, P., & O’Cass, A. (2011). Achieving superior innovation-based performance outcomes in SMEs through innovation resource-capability complementarity. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 40(8), 1285-1293.
- Stronen, F., Hoholm, T., Kvaerner, K. & Stome, L. N. (2017). Dynamic capabilities and innovation capabilities: The case of the innovation clinic. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*, 13(1), 89 – 116.

- Teece, D. J. (2017). Dynamic capabilities and (digital) platform lifecycles. In Furman, J., Gawer, A., Silverman, & Stern, S. (Eds.), *Organisational Resilience and Complex Systems. Journal of Management and Research (JMR)*, 6(1), 211–225.
- Teece, D., Pisano, G. & Shuen, S. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509 – 533.
- Verona, G., & Ravasi, D. (2003). Unbundling dynamic capabilities: An exploratory study of continuous product innovation. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 12(3), 577-606.
- Worley, G., T. Williams, E. & Lawler, E. (2014). *The agility factor. Building adaptable organizations for superior performance.* Jossey Bass.
- Wulandari, F. R., Supriyono, B., Muluk, M. R. K. & Setyowati, E. (2021). Dynamic capability model to increase creative economy competitiveness in Depok city, West Java, Indonesia. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 8(3), 780 – 791.
- Yusuf, Y. Y., Sarhadi, M., & Gunasekaran, A. (1999). Agile manufacturing: The drivers, concepts and attributes. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62, 33-43.
- Zahra, S.A. & George, G. (2002). The net enabled business innovation cycle and the evolution of dynamic capabilities. *Information Systems Research*, 13(2), 147-150.
- Zhao, L., Huo, B., Sun, L. and Zhao, X. (2013). The impact of supply chain risk on supply chain integration and company performance: A global investigation, supply chain management. *An International Journal*, 18(2), 115-131.
- Zollo, M., and Winter, S. G. (2002). Deliberate learning and the evolution of dynamic capabilities. *Organisation Science*, 13(3), 339–358.